

3rd CYCLONHIT SUMMER SCHOOL:

“Photoactivable antibacterials: from basic concepts to practical applications”

Bologna, September 26 – 28, 2016

VENUE: CNR Area della Ricerca
Via Piero Gobetti 101, 40129 Bologna

ORGANIZERS: Dr. Ilse Manet, ISOF-CNR
Prof. Salvatore Sortino, University of Catania

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